

Pesticidal Characteristics of Some New Organotin Phenols

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Manuscript received 22 April 1974; accepted 1 October 1974.

With a view to explore the pesticidal character of mercurated phenols, a series of organotin phenols, were synthesised using a range of substituted analogues containing $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{Cl}$ groups. In all thirteen compounds were thus prepared through stannation of mercurials using anhydrous stannous chloride in xylene. Their character, fungicidal and bactericidal properties were studied and most potent compounds identified.

PROMISEFUL role of organotin compounds, in preference to organomercurials, as multi-protecting reagents against important fungi and bacteria of cereal crops, observed earlier^{1,2} and the bactericidal behaviour of mercurated phenols prepared and reported by Sircar and Raut^{3,4} encouraged the authors to prepare new organotin phenols and study their pesticidal behaviour. Cartesi and Floury⁵ also observed fungistatic action of mercurated nitro-cresol on *Aspergillus niger* even at very low concentrations. Organotin compounds have an edge over organomercurials on account of their reduced hazards on mammals or other animals and their combined fungitoxicity, bacteritoxicity and enzymatic⁶ properties. A series of organotin phenols were, therefore, prepared by the method reported earlier² using substituted phenols which were initially mercurated with mercuric acetate and the acetoxymercury phenols so formed were converted into respective monochlorotin phenols involving the following general reaction.

mercuric acetate in presence of glacial acetic acid and ethanol by the method of Dimroth⁷. The thirteen resultant 2 or 4 acetoxymercury phenols so formed were, individually, converted into corresponding 2 or 4 monochlorotin-phenols by refluxing them on an oil bath for fourteen hours with equimolar anhydrous stannous chloride in presence of sodium dried xylene. The developed tin compounds isolated by removal of xylene were recrystallised in acetone or ethanol and their properties including the pesticidal characteristics studied by the method reported earlier using potato-dextrose-agar media for fungicidal and agar solidified nutrient media for bactericidal behaviour. The fungi selected for these studies included *Aspergillus niger* and *Chetomium globosum* and bacteria covering *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, which are most common fungi and bacteria in growth of cereal crops. The names and properties of compounds synthesised are listed in table.

Experimental

Phenol and its twelve other substituted analogues were mercurated with equimolar quantities of

The structure of the compounds were confirmed on the basis of the position of acetoxymercury group in mercurated compounds established earlier

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TABLE I—NAMES OF TIN COMPOUNDS AND PESTICIDAL PROPERTIES

Sl. No.	Nature of R	MP°C	Yield%	Colour	Tin percentage		Chlorine percentage		Pesticidal properties			
					Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Antifungal A.N.	Antibacterial C.G	E.C.	S.A.
1	Phenol	140	50	Y	47.1	47.6	14.0	14.3	-	+	+	+
2	2-CH ₃	165	48	B	45.0	45.2	13.2	13.6	+	+	+	+
3	3-CH ₃	163	52	DB	53.8	54.0	15.8	16.2	+	+	++	+
4	4-CH ₃	178	50	Y.O	44.8	45.2	13.3	13.6	+	-	-	-
5	3-OH	162	43	Y.B	44.6	44.9	13.1	13.5	++	+	-	+
6	2-O CH ₃	106	52	G	42.3	42.6	12.4	12.8	++	++	+	++
7	2-NH ₂	202(d)	46	Y	44.7	45.1	13.0	13.5	-	-	-	-
8	4-NH ₂	180	50	Y.O	45.0	45.1	13.2	13.5	-	-	+	+
9	3-NO ₂	210(d)	49	C.B	40.2	40.4	11.5	12.1	-	+	+	+
10	4-NO ₂	230(d)	56	D.O	40.0	40.4	11.7	12.1	++	++	-	-
11	2-OH	152	48	Y	44.5	44.9	13.2	13.5	+	-	-	++
12	2-Cl	172(d)	53	A.G	41.6	41.9	24.8	25.2	++	+	-	-
13	3-Cl	180	54	Y	41.7	41.9	24.7	25.2	+	+	+	-

%stands for mortality upto 50 and ++ for more than 50%

- stands for negative mortality.

Y=Yellow, B=Brown, O=Orange, G=Grey, C=Chocolate, A=Ash, D=Dark, d=decomposed.

by Rohatgi⁸, Vishnoi and others and which formed the base of the present synthesis. The acetoxymercury group according to those authors occupy the ortho and para position and the stannous groups which completely replaces the acetoxymercury group naturally occupies those ortho and para positions. Complete replacement of mercury group was further established through estimation of metallic mercury separated as a result of stannation and which was found to be theoretically quantitative. The structures were further confirmed through gravimetric determinations of mercury and tin contents by Lamholt and Christiansen's method. These were compared against the theoretical values and found to be in closed proximation.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of the data in the table would reflect a fair efficiency of the synthetic method as a result of which 46-56% of the theoretical yields of the tin compounds have been obtained. The compounds containing -NH₂ and -NO₂ group had slightly higher melting point than the other substituents. The pesticidal properties were strongest in compounds containing 4-NO₂ and 2-O CH₃ groups against both the fungi, *Aspergillus niger* and *Chetomium globosum*. The fungicidal activity was also very potent in tin compounds associated with 3-OH and 2-Cl substituents in regard to *Aspergillus niger* even though they exhibited only mild toxicity against *Chetomium globosum*. The compounds containing 2, 3 and 4-CH₃ as well as 2-OH and 3-Cl groups were only mildly toxic against *Aspergillus niger* and occasionally against *Chetomium globosum*. This behaviour closely supports the observation of Zsolani¹¹ who reported nitration, halogenation and alkylation were most effective means of increasing their fungi toxicity. Addition of alkyl group by the halogenated phenols observed by the same author imparts marked improvement in fungi toxic behaviour. Nitration in ortho and para position, had also been reported by Merkel and Zawadowske¹² to improve the fungi toxic behaviour of phenoxy compound.

In regard to bactericidal behaviour of these compounds it was evident that the compounds

containing 3-CH₃ group in their nuclei imparted them maximum bactericidal character against *Escherichia coli*. Compounds containing phenol, 2-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 4-NH₂, 3-NO₂ and 3-Cl groups exhibited only mild toxicity against this bacteria.

The bactericidal behaviour was more pronounced in case of 2-O CH₃ and 2-OH substituted compounds which proved extremely potent against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Other substituents exhibiting mild toxicity against this bacteria were 2 and 3-CH₃, 3-OH, 4-NH₂ and 3-NO₂ groups.

It would be amply established that the organotin phenolic compounds are potent multipurpose pesticides when they contain 3-CH₃, 2-O CH₃, 2-CH₃ groups in their benzene ring. The 3-OH and 2-Cl substituents impart marked toxicity against fungi and 4-NH₂ and 3-NO₂ group against bacteria. These characters can be exploited to greatest advantage in plant protection work.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the authorities of Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur, for providing facilities of the work.

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